

Quick Starting Guide FLexGripPlus - Simulation

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The Quick Starting Guide of **FlexGripPlus GPU model** allows the configuration and launching of simulation using one of the versions of the FlexGripPlus GPU model.

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The open-source **FlexGripPlus GPU** model can be downloaded from:

<https://github.com/Jerc007/Open-GPGPU-FlexGrip->

Version 1.0

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ORGANIZATION

The FlexGripPlus model is organized as a set of descriptive files and several compilation files for different simulators.

Initially, you find a set of folders as shown in the picture:

The **FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed** folder includes all files to build the GPU model and also to perform the compilation. The **Test_Programs** folder is an alternative place to locate the parallel program (kernel) to be executed in the GPU model.

The **RTL** folder stores all hardware descriptions of the main components of the **FlexGripPlus GPU model**.

The **Lib_m** and **Lib_x** stores the fast compilation files for ModelSim and Xcelium Parallel Simulator, respectively.

The organization and hierarchy of the files of the FlexGripPlus GPU model can be consulted in the project hierarchy scheme, see project_hierarchy.pdf file.

START A SIMULATION

From a terminal enter the **Lib_m** or **Lib_x** folder:

```
/4.4_FlexGripPlus_FP_SFU_3.0/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m>
```

Then, use the .TCL or python scripts to compile and start a simulation of the GPU model.

For ModelSim, QuestaSim or ModelSim-Altera Starter Edition:

```
/4.4_FlexGripPlus_FP_SFU_3.0/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m> vsim -do gpgpu_compile.tcl
```

For Xcelium Parallel Simulator:

```
/4.4_FlexGripPlus_FP_SFU_3.0/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_x> python launch_X.py █
```

Issues during the compilation and simulation

In case of errors during the compilation with ModelSim for Windows, please open in the tool bar: Compile/Compile Options...

then, in the window select:

Finally, apply and accept changes. Most common errors are due to the optimization of the StdLogic 1164 library. Please launch again the compilation.

If the errors persist, please check the presence of the following files in each one of the folders:

File	Folder
<i>global_mem.mif</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m
<i>constant_mem.mif</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m
<i>system_mem.mif</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m
<i>pick_bech.vhd</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/TP
<i>TP_instructions.vhd</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/TP
<i>TP_configuration.vhd</i>	main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/TP

NOTE: some versions of ModelSim for windows would require the administrator execution to read the files during the compilation.

CHANGE THE PARALLEL PROGRAM TO EXECUTE

Three main files are required to perform the execution of one parallel program in the FlexGripPlus model:

- **Data memory:** The input data values copied from the host to the device (*Global_mem.mif*)
- **Device configuration:** The configuration of the device from the program kernel (*pick_bech.vhd*)
- **Kernel instructions:** The instructions to be executed in the FlexGripPlus model (*TP_instructions.vhd*)

There are two methods to change the parallel program to be executed.

- 1) The first option requires the specific placement of each file in the folders.
 - Enter the folder of the global memory file:
Path: main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_m
or
Path: main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/lib_x
and replace the ***global_mem.mif*** file.
 - Enter the configuration folder in the path:
Path: main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/configuration
and replace the ***pick_bench.vhd*** file.
 - Enter the folder:
Path: main_folder_FlexGripPlus/FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/TP
and replace the ***TP_instructions.vhd*** file.

NOTE: The folder path... FlexGripPlus_Pro_ed/RTL/TB/TP also contains the ***global_mem.mif*** file. However, it is only employed during the fault simulation campaigns. Fault simulation campaigns are out of the scope of this manual. Please consult the Fault simulator manual for additional information.

- 2) The second option is a simplified version and automatizes the location of the files on each folder. For this purpose, locate the three new files inside the ***Test_Programs*** folder and use the ***Execute_simulation_modelsim_(linux/windows).py*** file to launch the compilation of the GPU model.

OBSERVE SIMULATION RESULTS

Once the simulation is executed, there are two methods to observe the results of a simulation: waveforms and output memory file.

If a program kernel is executed correctly, there are four major stages of the simulation: the GPU configuration, the kernel execution, the memory results retrieval and the finishing of the simulation. In the next Figure, it is possible to observe the waveforms of a correct simulation and also the four stages. It is worth noting that the simulation of the **FlexGripPlus GPU** model also includes the configuration procedures and the retrieval of memory results.

In the Figure, the SMP PROCESSING state of the test_bench_state_machine represents the operative state of the GPU model, so executing each instruction from the parallel kernel. It must be noted that the execution time is dependent on the application kernel and the configuration parameters. The DONE state must be reached if the simulation is correct, and can be checked when ModelSim ask for closing after finishing and stoping the simulation.

Once a simulation is finished, one .log file is generated as the output memory (retrieved from the device). This file (***gpgpu_rdata.log***) contains addresses and values of the output memory after the execution of the parallel application.

NOTE: if the simulation does not reach the DONE state, the *gpgpu_rdata.log* is not correctly generated.

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1	00000	4080565C
2	00004	4088596B
3	00008	40FE5B55
4	0000C	3F5F4F25
5	00010	410B6C03
6	00014	3F74394C
7	00018	4061A72A
8	0001C	3FF66E80
9	00020	40B8B472
10	00024	3F0B5B70
11	00028	3EB44A6A
12	0002C	40C4668A
13	00030	400AD125
14	00034	40FDC062
15	00038	4070497F
16	0003C	40F18343
17	00040	3F005E30
18	00044	401D08C6
19	00048	4103109A
20	0004C	40D5D2B2
21	00050	3D425099
22	00054	40B718AF
23	00058	410B1C2D
24	0005C	40E5F2B4